

A Multigenerational Workforce: The Perceived Working Environment and Support of Selected Employees within Metro Manila

Rouella Moyano-Baluyut, BSA¹; Ryan Liberato, BS CompEng² and Francis Michael P. Yambao, PhD³

^{1,2,3} Centro Escolar University

Received: 28.01.2025 | **Accepted:** 30.01.2025 | **Published:** 30.01.2025

***Corresponding Author:** Rouella Moyano-Baluyut, BSA¹

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14799694](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14799694)

Abstract	Original Research Article
<p>Having a multigenerational workforce working in a common workplace presents unique challenges and opportunities. Focusing mainly on Baby Boomers, Generation X, Millennials, and Generation Z, this study investigates the working environment and support among employees from different generational groups within Metro Manila. This study will use and utilize a quantitative approach to provide understanding how generational differences affect job satisfaction, productivity, and workplace dynamics.</p> <p>Despite differences among generations, this study identifies common factors that play a part to a positive working environment and opportunities for cross-generational mentoring.</p> <p>The research emphasizes the need for customized support strategies in order to meet the unique needs of different generation groups. By promoting an inclusive and supportive workplace, this provides valuable insights for organizations that aim to enhance their employee engagement and improve performance across generations.</p> <p>Keywords: Baby Boomers, Generation X, Millennials, Generation Z, workplace, multigenerational.</p>	

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims to address the gap by looking at the perceived working environment and support among employees from different generational groups within Metro Manila.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the demographic profile of the respondents according to their:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Year of Service
 - 1.3 Job roles?

2. What is the perceived working environment and support of the respondents?
3. How the perceived working environment and support compare between
 - 3.1 Generation X
 - 3.2 Millennials
 - 3.3 Generation Z?

INTRODUCTION

We are in an era where we experience

generational diversity in the modern workforce. This multigenerational composes of Baby Boomers, Generation X, Millennials, and Generation Z, as they have different generational characteristics, preferences and communication shaped by their historical, cultural, and exposure to technology. In Metro Manila, this workforce setup presents both opportunities and challenges for organizations making great efforts to create a positive and inclusive environment.

This study aims to explore the perceived working environment and support employees that belong from different generational groups within

Metro Manila. By studying the experiences of Baby Boomers, Generation X, Millennials, and Generation Z, this study seeks to identify the commonalities and differences in their workplaces perceptions. Findings will provide insights for organizations as they looking to enhance employee engagement and improve performance across generational lines.

A multigenerational workforce brings unique ideas and approaches in problem-solving as each generation offers distinct ways of thinking (Orduña, 2024). Table 1 shows the different generation covered in this study and when they were born:

Table 1: The different generations and their age as of 2024

Generation	Year of Birth	Current Age
Baby Boomers	1946-1964	60-78
Generation X	1965-1980	44-59
Millennials	1981-1996	28-43
Generation Z	1997-2012	12-30

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, it reviews existing literature focusing on the definition and importance of multigenerational workforce and their differences in values, work ethics, and expectations. This section will also cover how to manage and support a multigenerational workforce.

Definition of Multigenerational Workforce

A multigenerational workforce includes workers from multiple generations who bring different experiences, values and perspectives to the workplace. Historical events, cultural shifts, societal norms, parenting styles, technology and more help shape workers in various generational cohorts. While members of a multigenerational workforce may share similar characteristics, their work styles and expectations often differ (Kuligowski, 2024).

Recent Study: A study by AARP across 36 OECD countries shows support for

multigenerational workforce changes (Perron, 2020). After defining a multigenerational workforce, it is important for us to dive in and understand their unique characteristics and values of each cohort. By understanding these, organizations create a productive working environment.

Understanding Generational Differences

(*Baby Boomers: The Gloomiest Generation*, 2008) Survey reveals that Baby Boomers, those born between 1946 and 1964, are more pessimistic about their lives compared to younger and older generations. Despite having the highest incomes, Boomers are concerned about their financial future, believing their incomes won't keep up with inflation. They also feel it's harder to get ahead now than it was a decade ago and are less likely to say their standard of living is better than their parents' at the same age. This generation's gloomy outlook has persisted for over two decades, influenced by both their current stage of life and long-standing attitudes formed in

their youth. They are known for their economic and political influence, but many face financial challenges as they approach (Investopedia Team, 2024). They contributed to major social changes, including civil rights, women's rights, and antiwar movements. They were instrumental in fostering a culture of activism and volunteerism, inspired by leaders like John F. Kennedy (McCullough, n.d.). The Baby Boom was unique because it reversed a long trend of declining fertility rates, which had been associated with rising incomes (Arslanagic & Sarygulov, 2023).

Generation X is the demographic cohort following the Baby Boomers and preceding the Millennials. This generation is characterized by its experiences of economic and technological change, cultural shifts, and a balance of traditional and modern values (*Understanding Generation X*, n.d.). are typically less dramatic and more stable (Gao & Taylor, 2014). They grew up during significant societal and technological changes, such as the rise of dual-income families and rapid technological advancements (*What Is Generation X or Gen X?*, n.d.).

Recent Study: According to (Gao & Taylor, 2014), Generation X often acts as a bridge between the larger Baby Boomer and Millennial generation. They are savvy, skeptical and self-reliant.

Millennials have been significantly affected by the Great Recession, leading to high levels of student debt and delayed milestones like homeownership and starting families. They value experiences over material possessions, prioritize work-life balance, and are more likely to live with their parents longer than previous generations (Buckley et al., 2015). They are the first generation to grow up with digital technology as an integral part of their lives (Keeter & Taylor, 2009)

Recent Study: Millennials' experiences with digital technology and economic challenges are well-documented. (Buckley et al., 2015)and (Keeter & Taylor, 2009) provide insights into how these factors shape their work preferences and life choices.

Generation Z is the first generation to grow up with the internet, making them highly adept with technology. Their identity has been influenced by significant events like climate change, the financial crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic (*What Is Gen Z*, 2024). They are more racially and ethnically diverse

than previous generations and are on track to be the most well-educated generation yet. Gen Z is more familiar with and supportive of gender-neutral pronouns and other social changes. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted their economic prospects, with many experiencing job losses or pay cuts (Igielnik & Parker, 2020). They are cautious with finances, preferring to save and avoid debt, influenced by witnessing the Great Recession (Nunez & Rodriguez, 2024).

Recent Study: Generation Z's technological adeptness and cautious financial behavior are shaped by significant events such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the Great Recession able them to diversify their income sources to ensure financial stability (Igielnik & Parker, 2020; Nunez & Rodriguez, 2024).

Now that with a clear understanding of generational differences, next step is for us to explore effective management strategies. These strategies are designed to leverage the strengths of each generation while addressing the potential conflicts.

Strategies for Effective Management

Workplaces have served as gathering spaces for generations of workers in pursuit of success, but, just as important, as places where people find fulfillment, a sense of belonging, and opportunities to learn and grow (Rishi et al., 2021). Newspaper stories, consultant press releases, magazine articles, and increasingly books are not hard to find exhorting that there are different generational cohorts in the workforce (Macky et al., 2008). It emphasizes setting clear goals and expectations to align all generations, encouraging cross-generational mentoring, and embracing ideas regardless of seniority. Additionally, it highlights the importance of communication, addressing stereotypes, and mutual respect. These are just some of the common strategies to create a cohesive and productive work environment and create a cohesive and productive work environment (Ashraf, 2018; Pinto, 2024; *Strategies for Managing a Multigenerational Workforce*, n.d.)

As organizations implement these strategies, it is normal that they may encounter various challenges. Addressing these challenges that are agreeable to all generations is the key to maintaining a cohesive and productive multigenerational

workforce.

Challenges and Solutions

Age-based stereotypes can lead to discrimination, with older employees seen as resistant to change and younger ones viewed as inexperienced. Each generation has its preferred communication style, which can lead to miscommunication. As they have Different life stages mean varying priorities, from career advancement to work-life balance. For these to address, generational diversity a priority in hiring and retention practices Use a mix of communication tools to cater to different preferences, such as emails for Boomers and instant messaging for Millennials and Offer flexible working arrangements to accommodate different life stages and needs (Gates, n.d.).

METHODOLOGY

This study will use the Descriptive-quantitative design used to systematically collect

and analyze numerical data to describe a phenomenon.

1. Frequency and Percentage- for the demographic profile of the respondents.
2. Mean and standard deviation- for the perceived working environment and support of the respondents
3. T-test - for comparison of the perceived working environment and support of the respondents

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data gathered in the questionnaire answered by the respondents, the following analysis is observed:

Table 2 presents the demographic data based on the age, years of service and job title of the respondents. Majority of them or 43% of the respondents belong to the 28-43 age bracket or Generation X. Most of them have already rendered 3-5 years of service in their company. And more than half or 51% classified as rank and file employees.

Table 2: Demographic of the respondents

Description	Category	N	%
Age	20-23	5	14%
	24-27	9	26%
	28-43	15	43%
	44-59	6	17%
Years of Service	Less than 1 Year	4	11%
	1-2 years	8	23%
	3-5 years	15	43%
	6-9 years	3	9%
	10 and above	5	14%
Job	Rank and file	18	51%
	Senior Staff	14	40%
	Others (not Specified)	3	9%

About their workplace environment, Table 3 shows that the respondents perceived that they have a good workplace environment. They describe their overall

work culture well, they feel inclusive in their workplace, and they have a good level of collaboration within their team.

Table 3: Workplace Environment

Description	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
How would you describe the overall work culture at your company?	4.26	0.74	Good
How inclusive do you feel the workplace is?	4.26	0.78	Good
How would you rate the level of collaboration within your team?	4.34	0.72	Good

As to communication and feedback, table 4 shows that they usually received feedback on their performance quarterly. They feel comfortable

sharing their ideas and opinions with their colleagues monthly. Their preferred communication style at work is neither instant messaging nor face to face.

Table 4: Communication and Feedback

Description	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
How often do you receive feedback on your performance?	3.24	0.96	Quarterly
Do you feel comfortable sharing your ideas and opinions with your colleague?	3.87	1.20	Monthly

Table 5 shows the career development of the respondents. They perceived that having a clear career progression plan is extremely important. They are somewhat satisfied with the professional

development opportunities provided by their companies. Among the training or development programs they find most beneficial are training related to Leadership and Technical Skills.

Table 5: Career Development

Description	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
How important is it for you to have a clear career progression plan?	4.77	0.49	Extremely Important
How satisfied are you with the professional development opportunities provided by the company?	4.06	0.76	Somewhat Satisfied

In table 6, work life balance shows importance among the respondents. They feel that work-life

balance is extremely important. They said that their current work-life balance is good. They also feel that

the company they're in supports their mental health and well being. They preferred the hybrid part-time

in the office and part-time remote as their work arrangements.

Table 6: Work Life Balance

Description	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
How important is work-life balance to you?	4.89	0.40	Extremely Important
How would you rate your current work-life balance?	4.23	0.73	Good
Do you feel that your company supports your mental health and well-being?	2.60	0.55	Yes

The job satisfaction and productivity is reflected in table 7. They feel neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their current job. Maybe they perceived their performance to affect working with

different generations. They most enjoyed the collaboration, teamwork, camaraderie, and flexibility.

Table 7: Job Satisfaction and Productivity

Description	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
How satisfied are you with your current job role?	3.34	1.4	Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied
Does your performance affect working with different generations?	2.17	0.89	Maybe

Table 8 shows the comparison of the different determinants as perceived by the respondents. The Workplace Environment, Communication and Feedback, and Career Development are significant to

the respondents while the Work Life Balance and Job Satisfaction and Productivity are perceived not significant.

Table 8: Generational Perception of the Different Determinants of Working Environment and Support

Age	Determinants	Weighted Average	Interpretation
	Workplace Environment	.02	Significant

44-59 12-30	28-43	Communication and Feedback	.06	Significant
		Career Development	.06	Significant
		Work Life Balance	.13	Not Significant
		Job Satisfaction and productivity	.30	Not Significant

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research study focuses on the working environment and support of the multigenerational workforce of selected employees in OpenText Philippines, Centro Escolar University-Manila and other companies in Metro Manila. Among the 5 determinants analyzed, Work life balance and job

satisfaction and productivity are found not significant as perceived by the respondents. While the Workplace Environment, Communication and Feedback, and Career Development are perceived significant by the respondents. With this, it is recommended to come up with some strategies based on the significant perception of the respondents as follows:

Areas of Concern	Strategy/ Activity	Benefits	Time Framed
Workplace Environment	Activity 1. Employee Value Proposition Development Objectives: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct a surveys to gather inputs from employees about what they value most in their workplace 2. Develop a clear Employee Value Proposition that highlights benefits a\that aligned with the needs of different 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduce employee turnover 2. Increase employee engagement 3. Cost Saving on employee recruitment 4. Positive workplace culture 	Year-round Activity

	<p>generations</p> <p>3. Communicate the Employee Value Proposition effectively through the different channels available to ensure that the employees are aware of the existing benefits and maximize the use of it.</p>		
Communication and Feedback	<p>Activity 2. Cross-Generational training workshop</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide a training sessions focussing on the improvement of the cross-generational communication skills 2. Encourage sharing ideas among employees from different generations <p>Activity 2. Regular Feedback Mechanism</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implement a structured feedback mechanism in 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhance collaboration among employees 2. Improve overall workplace morale 3. Increase productivity through a more effective teamwork and communication <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Empowers employees by giving them opportunities to share their thoughts in the 	<p>2-4 months to conduct a training and follow-up session every 6 months</p> <p>Immediate implementation of feedback mechanism and semi-annual reviews to analyze</p>

	<p>order to assess the communication effectiveness</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Encourage an open dialogue during team meetings where employees can share their thoughts and experiences related to communication. 3. Act on the gathered feedback by developing a plan to ensure continuous improvement 	<p>issues related to communication strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Identifies areas for improvement 3. Build trust among employees as they see that their feedback is acted upon. 	<p>feedback and make necessary adjustments</p>
Career Development	<p>Activity 1. Continuous Learning Opportunities</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide learning opportunities such as workshops, online courses and morale and job satisfaction others that tailored to the different learning styles and preferences 2. Encourage participation and facilitate 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve employee morale and job satisfaction 2. Enhance organizational performance 3. Improve retention rates of employees 	<p>1-3 months to establish initial learning opportunities and a year-round related activity</p>

	<p>skill sharing and collaborative learning experiences</p> <p>3. Assess training programs to ensure they meet the evolving needs of employees across generations</p>		
--	---	--	--

In the light of the results of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. To the employees, they are encouraged to actively engage in the communication initiatives, participate in the training related to the cross-generational and take advantage of the career development opportunities and the existing development opportunities in their companies.
2. To researchers, they can consider researching assessment of the impacts of the implemented strategies on employee satisfaction and productivity within a multigenerational workforces. They can investigate how the different generations adapt to the new technologies in the workforces and

identify best practices in facilitating this transition. Also, they can examine the role of Employee Value Proposition (EVP), how it influences employee engagement and retention among different generations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to express our deepest gratitude to all those who provided us with the possibility to complete this research. To Dr. Sonia L. Pilao and Dr. Francis Michael P. Yambao, whose expertise added considerably to our graduate experience.

We would also like to thank our colleagues and classmates for their support in writing this research paper.

REFERENCES

- Arslanagic, P., & Sarygulov, A. (2023, September 7). *Understanding the Baby Boom*. Works in Progress. Retrieved December 3, 2024, from <https://worksinprogress.co/issue/understanding-the-baby-boom/>
- Ashraf, R. (2018, January). Multigenerational Employees: Strategies for Effective Management. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*, 7. 10.4172/2162-6359.1000528
- Baby Boomers: The Gloomiest Generation*. (2008, June 25). Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2008/06/25/baby-boomers-the-gloomiest-generation/>
- Bailey, E., & Owens, C. (2020, September). *Unlocking the Benefits of the Multigenerational Workplace*. Harvard Business. https://www.harvardbusiness.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Unlocking-the-Benefits-of-Multigenerational-Workforces_Aug-2020.pdf
- Buckley, P., Viechnicki, P., & Barua, A. (2015, October). A new understanding of Millennials: Generational differences reexamined. *Issues by the Numbers*.
- Gao, G., & Taylor, P. (2014, June 5). *Generation X: America's neglected 'middle child'*. Pew Research Center. Retrieved December 3, 2024, from <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2014/06/05/generation-x-americas-neglected-middle-child/>
- Gates, M. (n.d.). *Generational Diversity in the Workplace: 6 Ways to Foster It & Support a Multigenerational Workforce*. Power to Fly. <https://powertofly.com/up/challenges-of-managing-a-multigenerational-workforce>
- Igielnik, R., & Parker, K. (2020, May 14). *On the Cusp of Adulthood and Facing an Uncertain Future: What We Know About Gen Z So Far*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2020/05/14/on-the-cusp-of-adulthood-and-facing-an-uncertain-future-what-we-know-about-gen-z-so-far/>
- Investopedia Team. (2024, June 8). *Baby Boomer: Definition, Age Range, Characteristics, and Impact*. Investopedia. https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/baby_boomer.asp#:~:text=%E2%80%9CBaby%20boomer%E2%80%9D%20is%20a%20term,population%2C%20especially%20in%20developed%20nations
- Keeter, S., & Taylor, P. (2009, December 10). *The Millennials*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/2009/12/10/the-millennials/>
- Kuligowski, K. (2024, October 25). *How to Work With a Multigenerational Workforce*. Business.com. Retrieved November 29, 2024, from <https://www.business.com/articles/hiring-multigenerational-workforce/>
- Macky, K., Gardner, D., & Forsyth, S. (2008). Generational differences at work: introduction and overview. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 23(8), 857-861. 10.1108/02683940810904358
- McCullough, K. (n.d.). *What Are Baby Boomers Known For – Understanding Boomers and Their Contribution*. Karen McCullough. Retrieved December 3, 2024, from <https://www.karenmccullough.com/understanding-boomers-contribution/>
- Nunez, I., & Rodriguez, M. A. (2024, January 15). *To understand Generation Z today is to glimpse a radically different future*. Telefonica. <https://www.telefonica.com/en/communication-room/blog/to-understand-generation-z-today-is-to-glimpse-radically-different-future/>
- Orduña, C. (2024, November 27). *Your Guide to Managing a Multigenerational Workforce*. CareerMinds. <https://careerminds.com/blog/managing-multigenerational-workforce>
- Perron, R. (2020, August 10). *Insights from Global Employers: The Future of Work is Living, Learning and Earning Longer*. AARP. Retrieved December 5, 2024, from <https://www.aarp.org/pri/topics/work-finances-retirement/employers-workforce/global-employer-survey/>
- Pinto, P. (2024, September 23). *Managing Multigenerational Teams Effectively: Key strategies for workplace harmony*. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/managing->

multigenerational-teams-effectively-key-
pedro-c4gxf

Rishi, S., Breslau, B., & Miscovich, P. (2021). *The Workplace You Need Now: Shaping Spaces for the Future of Work*. Wiley.

Strategies for Managing a Multigenerational Workforce. (n.d.). Corporate Class Inc. <https://www.corporateclassinc.com/strategies-multigenerational-workforce/>

Understanding Generation X. (n.d.). All Voices.

<https://www.allvoices.co/glossary/generation-x>

Waldman, E. (2021, September 1). *How to Manage a Multi-Generational Team*. Harvard Business Review.

<https://hbr.org/2021/08/how-to-manage-a-multi-generational-team>

What Is Generation X or Gen X? (n.d.). BambooHR. Retrieved December 3, 2024, from

<https://www.bamboohr.com/resources/hr-glossary/generation-x>

What is Gen Z. (2024, August 28). McKinsey & Company.

<https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-is-gen-z/>